

Neodymium budget in the Mediterranean Sea: Evaluating the role of atmospheric dusts using a high-resolution dynamical-biogeochemical model

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Tracer of circulation

Tachikawa et al, 2004

Proxy of past of circulation

Dubois-dauphin et al, 2016

Objective

Determine and quantify the different sources and the internal cycle involved in the Nd cycle in the Med Sea.

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Method

explicit modelling of Nd cycle with the high resolution model NEMO-MED12/PISCES

NEMO-MED12 bathymetry

External inputs and boundary conditions of Nd

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Sédiment

(Ayache et al., 2016)

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Rivers

e.g. Tachikawa et al., 2004

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Dépôts atmosphériques

e.g. Scheuvers et al., 2013

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Sédiment

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External inputs and boundary conditions of Nd

Dépôts atmosphériques

e.g. Scheuvers et al., 2013

Rivers

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Internal Cycle - PISCES

Aumont and Bopp, 2006

Sédiment

(Ayache et al., 2016)

Vertical cycling (savenging) : biogeochemical model PISCES

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- **Big particles**
- 50 m/day at the surface to 300 m/day at depth
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3) Equilibrium partition coefficient K

- Estimated from data and previous modelling studies.

$$K = \frac{Nd_p}{Nd_d C_p}$$

Results: Evaluation of the impact of the external sources on the Nd cycle

Determine and quantify the different sources : **Nd concentration** (pmol/kg)

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SedRiv: BE as the unique source

SedRiv: BE + river waters

Results: Evaluation of the impact of the external sources on the Nd cycle

Determine and quantify the different sources : **Nd concentration** (pmol/kg)

- ✓ Very low concentrations in surface water
- ✓ Low impact of dissolved fluvial material on [Nd] in the Med Sea.

- ✓ Adding the atmospheric deposition considerably improve the performance of the model

SedRiv: BE as the unique source

SedRiv: BE + river waters

SedRivDust: BE + river waters + atmospheric dust.

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✓ Dusts inputs improve largely the simulation of ϵNd .

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Results: Nd Mediterranean budget from the different sources

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Desert dust deposition events are more frequent affecting a large spatial domain

The sensitivity test The spatial distribution of Nd in the atmospheric dust.

Nd observation in dust, from scheveuns et al, 2013

Dust deposition from Aladin, Nabat et al 2015

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Input/boundary conditions

3 sensitivity simulation:

Dust-CST: constant ϵ_{Nd} and $[Nd]$.

Dust-EWbasin constant value for each basin.

Dust-Sbbasin: one value for each sub-basin

The sensitivity test The spatial distribution of Nd in the atmospheric dust.

3 sensitivity simulation:

The εNd is more sensitive to the spatial distribution of Nd in the atmospheric dust.

Sensitivity tests on Internal cycle: scavenging coefficient Kd

3) Equilibrium partition coefficient K

- Estimated from data and previous modelling studies.

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Nd concentration

Nd Isotopic distribution

BE + River runoff

- Nd concentrations are too low in surface and intermediate water
- Too-radiogenic value in the surface water

BE + River runoff + Atmospheric dusts

- Atmospheric dust input has largely improved simulated Nd distribution
- Maximum concentration of Nd in intermediate water of EMed

Magnitude of Nd sources

- The results confirm the dominance of “BE” with 90 % of total flux.
- The flux of Nd from partially dissolved atmospheric dusts represent 7 % of total flux.
- The scavenging/remineralisation considerably constraints the ability of the model to simulate the vertical profile of ϵ_{Nd}

Motivations

high concentration in the surface water that suggests a significant impact of external sources

The simplified approach simulated too-radiogenic ϵNd values in the Mediterranean Sea

Desert dust deposition events are more frequent affecting a large spatial domain

Boudary exchange:
making of a map of ϵ_{nd}
along the continental margin

❑ EARTHCHEM: more than 2000 values, 600 references

Type of data extracted:

- Surface sediments deposited on margins (top core)
- Solid discharges from rivers
- Fields and outcropping rocks along the coast

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Interpolation and extrapolation on the margin of the model

- Type of data extracted:
- Surface sediments deposited on margins (top core)
 - Solid discharges from rivers
 - Fields and outcropping rocks along the coast

Ayache et al, 2016